

A study to assess efficacy of Hoffman's exercise and it's relationship to successful breastfeeding among antenatal mothers in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Tamil Nadu

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breastfeeding is the natural way of feeding a newborn. Breast milk has been shown to transmit several health benefits from mother to child. It is the perfect nourishment for a baby. Breastfeeding mothers may experience a variety of breast deformities, including long or short nipples, flat or inverted nipples, and cracked nipples, which can make feeding difficult.

Aim: To assess efficacy of Hoffman's exercise and its relationship to successful breastfeeding among antenatal mothers

Methods: A quasi-experimental study was conducted among 60 antenatal mothers, at Trichy SRM Medical College, Hospital.

Results: The study concluded that in control group majority (80%) of primipara mothers were medium risk and 20% of them were low risk whereas in experimental group 73% of them were low risk and 27% of them had medium risk

Conclusions: it was concluded that the Hoffman's exercise was an effective intervention on successful breastfeeding among antenatal mothers.

Keywords: Hoffman, Trichy, Breastfeeding, Antenatal, Nipple

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is the natural way of feeding a newborn child. Breast milk has been shown to transmit a lot of health benefits from mother to kid¹. It is the baby's perfect nourishment. Additionally, nursing forges a special link between the mother and child and gives the child enough warmth, security, affection, and protection^{2,3}.

According to the World Health Organization (2018), more than 820,000 newborn deaths may be avoided annually if all babies were exclusively breastfed until they were six months old⁴. Breastfeeding lowers the risk of malnutrition, promotes learning, and helps shield a kid against obesity and chronic diseases in the future⁵. Additionally, it facilitates birth spacing, quick postpartum recovery, and a quicker return to pre pregnancy weight⁶. Research indicates that women also had a lesser chance of developing breast and ovarian malignancies in later life, as well as less postpartum depression^{7,8}.

First-time breastfeeding mothers need support, encouragement, and skilled help because they are in a vulnerable situation^{9,10}. There are a wide range of potential breast abnormalities that mothers who are nursing could have⁶. Recognizing this problem is crucial to maintain a healthy breastfeeding relationship with the kid¹¹. Obstetricians have a dual responsibility of encouraging breastfeeding and making sure expectant mothers are physically fit to care for their unborn children¹². The detection and treatment of nipple abnormalities is an area that is frequently overlooked. It's critical to examine the areola and nipple to find any abnormalities^{2,7}.

Breastfeeding mothers may experience difficulties in initiating and sustaining breastfeed if they have inverted or nonprotractile breasts, which affects approximately 10% of expectant mothers^{4,13}. These ladies have been counselled to prepare their breasts for pregnancy for over 50 years; the most popular forms of treatment are Hoffman's exercise and breast shells^{14,15}.

The purpose of this study is to more effectively improve breastfeeding. Due to the paucity of research on the Hoffman's technique's efficacy for flat and inverted nipples in expectant mothers, as well as the possibility that inadequate feeding may contribute to postpartum depression and lower quality of life,

METHODS

Study Design & Area:

A quasi-experimental study was conducted among antenatal mothers attending Obstetrics and Gynaecology OPD at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital, Trichy, Tamil Nadu for a period of 6 months between March 2023 to September 2023. In our study Hoffman's exercise was used as independent variable and level of breastfeeding was used as dependent variable. After obtaining ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee, a semi structured questionnaire was used to collect demographic data.

Sample size:

A sample size of 60 was taken for this study. The study participants were selected by convenient sampling technique.

Study procedure:

After obtaining ethical approval from Institutional Human Ethics Committee and permission at all levels to conduct the survey, after getting informed and written consent, a semi structured questionnaire was used to collect demographic data and risk factors of breastfeeding was assessed using VIA CHRISTI breastfeeding assessment scale. The sample is then divided into two groups experimental group and control group.

Hoffman's exercise is the stretching exercise that helps to pull the flat and inverted nipples out. It is done by placing the thumb of both hands opposite to each other at the base of the nipple and gently but firmly pulling the thumbs away from each other. Then the thumbs are rolled at the base of the nipple. This exercise has to be done 5 times a day. Mothers were educated about this procedure.

We collected demographic characters like age, residential area, socioeconomic status, education, occupation, type of family.

Statistical Analysis:

Collected data was entered in Microsoft excel and statistical analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Descriptive statistics formed the basis of the analysis. Percentages were evaluated for the categorical variables.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the distribution of mothers according to age group. Majority (18 in cases and 20 in control group) were in the age category of 20-25 years in both experimental and control group. Most of the participants from both groups (70% in cases and 80% in control group) were housewives and only few participants held some occupation. Almost half the participants from both groups (53.3% in cases and 46.7% in control group) belonged to middle class according to BG Prasad socioeconomic scale. Most of the participants were from rural area and most of the participants lived in joint families.

The association between experimental and control group were tested for homogeneity by using chi-square test. The result shows that occupation, education, type of family and habitat were found significant association between experimental and control group which reveals that both groups are nonhomogeneous.

The other demographic variables in experimental and control group had no significant association and it is interfered that both the groups are homogenous and comparable.

Table 2 shows that in experimental group there was medium risk 5 (16.7%) on the level of breastfeeding, bulk number of mothers 25(83.3%) had low risk on the level of breastfeeding. However, in control group, high percentage of mothers 25 (83 %) had medium risk on the level of breastfeeding, whereas 5(16.7%) had low risk on the level of breastfeeding

Table 3 shows that the association between post-test level of breastfeeding with demographic variables in Experimental group which was assessed by using chi-square test. The result reveals that there was no association between selected demographic variables and level of breastfeeding at $p < 0.05$ level.

Table 4 shows the association between post-test level of breastfeeding with demographic variables in control group which was assessed by using chi-square test. The result reveals that there was no association between selected demographic variables and level of breastfeeding at $p < 0.05$ level.

DISCUSSION

The present study data presented that level of breastfeeding after intervention in experimental group. The effectiveness was statistically tested by unpaired t-test to compare both the groups which manifested that $t=10.62$, $df=58$ the result was found to be significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Therefore, hypotheses were accepted. Hence, it was concluded that the Hoffman's exercise was an effective intervention on successful breastfeeding among antenatal mothers^{6,16}.

This finding was supported by a study conducted by Amanpreet et al¹⁷ on effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise on successful breast feeding among primipara mothers with flat and retracted nipples. The present study was conducted on 30 primipara mothers (15 in control group and 15 in experimental group) immediately after delivery. Experimental group received Hoffman's exercise. The levels of successful breast feeding were assessed in both groups. The study concluded that in control group majority (80%) of primipara mothers were medium risk and 20% of them were low risk whereas in experimental group 73 of them were low risk and 27% of them had medium risk. The overall mean percentage was 56% in control group whereas in experimental group 78% with 't' value 6.82, significant at $P < 0.05$

LIMITATIONS

The present study was done in a small town in South India and hence it cannot be generalised for the larger populations.

CONCLUSION

The present study was conducted among mothers to evaluate efficacy of Hoffman's exercise. There was a significant depletion in flat and retracted nipple of primipara mothers after practicing the Hoffman exercise, thus it has demonstrated to be an effective technique for reducing flat and retracted nipple. Therefore, this intervention should be encouraged as hospital policy and implemented as routine care for all the primipara mothers in the first stage of labour for reducing the problem of flat and retracted nipple¹².

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DECLARATIONS

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Conflict of interest: there is no conflict of interest

Ethical approval: institutional human ethics committee approval was obtained

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Table 1. Distribution of demographic characteristics

S.no.	Variables	Cases		Controls		X ²	dF	P value	
		N	%	N	%				
1.	Age	20-25 years	18	60	20	66.7	3.8	2	0.3
		26-30 years	10	33.3	8	26.6			
		>31 years	2	6.7	2	6.7			

2.	Occupation	Housewife	21	70	24	80	7.2	1	0.03
		Employed	9	30	6	20			
3.	Socioeconomic status	Upper middle	4	13.4	6	20	9.4	3	0.09
		Middle	16	53.3	14	46.7			
		Lower middle	10	33.3	10	33.3			
4.	Residence	Urban	8	26.7	11	36.7	7.8	1	0.02
		Rural	22	73.3	19	63.3			
5.	Family type	Nuclear	7	23.3	9	30	8.4	1	0.01
		Joint	23	76.7	21	70			

Table 2. Effectiveness of Hoffman's exercise in both groups

Level of breastfeeding	Cases		Controls	
	N	%	N	%
High risk	0	0	0	0
Medium risk	5	16.7	25	83.3
Low risk	25	83.3	5	16.7

Table 3. Association between breastfeeding and demographic variables in experimental group

S.no.	Variables	Medium risk	Low risk	X ²	dF	P value	
1.	Age	20-25 years	4	13	3.7	2	0.3
		26-30 years	1	11			
		>31 years	0	1			
2.	Occupation	Housewife	25	20	1.6	1	0.8
		Employed	5	5			
3.	Socioeconomic status	Upper middle	2	8	5.8	3	0.1
		Middle	2	10			
		Lower middle	1	7			
4.	Residence	Urban	3	22	2.7	2	0.5
		Rural	2	3			
5.	Family type	Nuclear	2	23	0.8	1	0.4

		Joint	3	2			
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Table 4. Association between breastfeeding and demographic variables in control group

S.no.	Variables	Medium risk	Low risk	X ²	dF	P value	
1.	Age	20-25 years	20	2	4.3	1	0.5
		26-30 years	5	3			
		>31 years	0	0			
2.	Occupation	Housewife	20	5	3.4	3	0.3
		Employed	5	0			
3.	Socioeconomic status	Upper middle	3	0	0.2	1	0.7
		Middle	18	3			
		Lower middle	4	2			
4.	Residence	Urban	20	1	0.87	1	0.9
		Rural	5	4			
5.	Family type	Nuclear	5	1	0.2	1	0.6
		Joint	20	4			